

METHODOLOGY FOR CONTROLLING TRAINING LOADS OF HIGHLY SKILLED BELT WRESTLERS

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Abstract: in this article, the development of a two-month planning methodology for training loadings, taking into account the content and dynamics of nagruzkas, the direction of which is specialized in the Greco-Roman struggle, has been created to optimize the training process, as well as provide information on the effectiveness of the preparation of Greco-Roman wrestlers for Responsible competitions.

Keywords: Belt wrestling, specialization, complexity, nagruzkas, dynamics, training, downloads, planning, methodology, optimization.

МЕТОДИКА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНЫМИ НАГРУЗКАМИ БОРЦОВ НА ПОЯСАХ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ

Аннотация: в данной статье для оптимизации тренировочного процесса создана разработка методики двухмесячного планирования тренировочных нагрузок с учетом содержания и динамики нагрузок, направление которой специализируется на греко-римской борьбе. , а также предоставить информацию об эффективности подготовки борцов греко-римского стиля к Ответственным соревнованиям.

Ключевые слова: Борьба на поясах, специализация, сложность, нагрузки, динамика, тренировка, загрузки, планирование, методика, оптимизация.

Relevance of the topic: Belt wrestling to solve training loads, tasks, preliminary and basic pedagogical experiments were carried out. In the initial experiment, studies were carried out in order to classify and determine the load values of exercises for planning and control in training structures in Belt Wrestling. The intended duration of the application of loadings, in which the direction, size and specialization of the training process in different structures are different, was determined. In Belt Wrestling, the features of planning and control of coordination complex loadings were checked.

Main part: depending on the content of the parameters of the loadings at the special training stage of the competition period, the dynamics of the indicators of the special training and physical working capacity of belt wrestlers were determined. In pedagogical experience, the effectiveness of the responsibility for planning and controlling the downloads in the training and training process of the wrestlers in the belt struggle proposed by US was substantiated in the experiment.

The training and training process of the training of qualified belt wrestlers was organized experiments in January and February 2022. At the first stage of the initial experiment, the situation of the issue was studied, based on the analysis of literature and the generalization of advanced practical experience. The content of the loadings used in the training and training process of of qualified belt wrestlers, fighting in different ways, was analyzed.

In order to be able to develop an information framework for the task of planning and monitoring training loadings in Belt combat, systematization and classification of training loadings were carried out. Sorvanov V. On a 33-point scale, the dimensions of the loadings were

determined. Goals were also set for the following training systems: training tasks, training, days, microcycles and stages.

In the second stage of the initial experiment, the wrestlers training of specialized loadings with different directions, dimensions and coordination complexity and the intended duration of loadings were checked. In the experiment, as part of 2 groups, 20 qualified belt wrestlers took part. The verification of the effectiveness of the proposed responsibility was carried out within the framework of the main pedagogical experience. Qualified belt wrestlers of 10 men participated in the experiment as part of the control and experimental groups. At the beginning and end of the experiment, an assessment of the execution of complex coordinated actions, methods and combinations was carried out.

It was recommended to apply training loadings indicated in histogram No. 1 and 2 on the sheep in relation to viewers. G.S. In the preparatory part of the training on Tumanyan, it is advisable to gradually carry the load that is given to the body, and in the main part to apply a wave-like load, and in the final part to gradually reduce the load. In this, it is possible to use mainly two peak loads, the reason for which three or more peak loads weigh for the organism of qualified wrestlers is known from the analysis of the literature.

Table-1

V.A.Sorvanov training intensity scale

Influencing directions in training	Heart contraction number min	Heart contraction number min 10^l	Evaluation in points
More aerobic	114	19	1
	120	20	2
	126	21	3
	132	22	4
	138	23	5
	144	24	6
	150	25	7
Mixed aerobic-anaerobic	156	26	8
	162	27	10
	168	28	12
	174	29	14
	180	30	17
Anaerobic glycolytic	186	31	21
	192	32	25
	198	33	33

G.S. Tumanyan noted that it is necessary to apply training in a more selective direction than complex training, depending on the level of tasks being solved in the training process. Also, the planning of the training process consists primarily in the organization of a system of plans, which provides for the implementation of complex goals that are interconnected.

V.Yu. Verkhoshinsky noted that when planning and programming the training process, especially during the competition period, it is necessary to take into account such interdependence

as relying on the psychic nagruzkas of athletes, "psychic emotional state-nagruzka-reaction-recovery" and unconditionally follow the path from the main strategic line, carrying out the correction of nagruzkas on the basis of the mentioned link.

Figure 1. Dynamics of cardiac contraction change

L.P.Matveev believes that improving sports training will have the following problems.

- the problem of determining the level of discrepancy between the planned and current parameters of the training process.

- the choice of the planned, measured composition of the training is the problem of determining the training parameters, their dynamics, dimensions, planned training cycles and periods.

- the problem of organizing the interdependence of planning and control within the framework of small, medium and large training cycles in the training process.

- the problem of introducing modern computer technologies into the organization of the training process.

A.S.Khomenkov believes that at the present stage, the main focus in big sports is the creation of organizational structures and services capable of quickly responding to the dynamic development of sports in the world, providing training and competition processes with new technologies, effectively stimulating the activities of athletes, coaches, scientists, service personnel, leaders and entire organizations.

Among the most important methodological principles at the moment are the following.

- dynamism of the preparatory system. It covers the direction of development of sports skills in flexible planning, changes in rules, international calendar and x.k.it sets out to make quick adjustments to programs based on regular study of the S as well as accounting.

- rational distribution of tools, styles and nagruzkas in the annual cycle, depending on the stage of preparation, to a significant degree individualization of training and competition processes, therefore encouraging various alternative approaches.

Commentators have concluded that the direction of progress of the training process is determined by the optimal variability of its microtools. This is due to the necessary changes in training tasks, exercises, rational exchange of training and weekends, in the directions of nagruzkas, etc.

Nowadays, the perception of planning the training process in belbogly wrestling has changed considerably. This is due to the requirements of some changes to the rules of the competition, which the competition competitions put in order to increase their viewership.

Conclusion at the moment, objective conditions have been created for a more high-quality planning of the training of wrestlers, in which a large experimental material is collected. Successful management of the training process of athletes requires taking into account two important conditions: firstly, a sharp increase in the size and intensity of nagruzkas (nagruzkas in high performance in modern sports are approaching the limit of biological norms); secondly, an equalization of the number parameters and skill level of training (in the experience of world leading athletes). Therefore, the optimization of the training structure and the construction of optimal training programs remain of the first level of importance.

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